

HUNGARIAN PRESIDENCY
COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

Desktop Analysis of the Outcomes of EU Youth Dialogue Cycles 1-10

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Produced for the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of European Union, August 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13771853

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1. Introduction

The EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD) is a flagship youth participation mechanism at EU level aiming to bring youth voices to EU policy making. Its main element is the dialogue between young people, youth organisations and policy and decision makers, as well as experts, researchers and other relevant civil society actors. It serves as a forum for continuous joint reflection and consultation on the priorities, implementation and follow-up of European cooperation in the field of youth.

The specific objectives of the EU Youth Dialogue are to:

- encourage the participation of young people in democratic life in Europe in line with Article 165 Treaty on the Functioning of European Union (TFEU);
- promote equal participation between young women and men;
- include diverse voices and to ensure openness to all young people to contribute to policy-shaping;
- bring about positive change in youth policy at local, regional, national and European level;
- strengthen young people's citizenship competencies and sense of belonging to the society and the European Union.

The EUYD builds on the achievements of the Structured Dialogue which preceded it and followed a similar structure.

Six cycles of the Structured Dialogue and five cycles of EU Youth Dialogue (including the current cycle; both mechanisms are thereafter referred to as “the dialogue”) have taken place as of 2024. Each cycle lasts for one and a half years and involves three Presidencies of the Council of the European Union (referred to as a Trio). During this time each Presidency (which lasts for six months) hosts an EU Youth Conference (EUYC) attended by young people and policy makers. Within most EUYCs, policy recommendations¹ are created by conference delegates. The intention is typically that these recommendations are shared with the EU Youth Working Party, who may use them to inform the Council of the EU Resolutions or Conclusions on Youth. Alongside the EUYCs, consultation with young people and implementation activities also take place at national levels and through International Non-Governmental Youth Organisations. European level reports of these activities are typically produced, and EUYC recommendations may be based upon these. One of the most significant sets of recommendations coming from the EUYCs is the [EU Youth Goals](#), which were created during the 6th Cycle of Structured Dialogue, and subsequently became a fulltext annex of the resolution relating to the EU Youth Strategy 2019-2027 ([2018/C 456/01](#)).

The Council of the EU adopts conclusions and resolutions to express a political position on a given topic. These types of documents only set up political commitments or positions - they are not foreseen in the treaties of the EU, therefore, they are not legally binding. In the field of Youth, the European Union has the competence to ‘intervene to support, coordinate or complement the action of its Member States’. Conclusions and resolutions are used primarily to invite EU Member States or EU institutions to take action on a specific issue within this field.

¹ Other terms are also used in lieu of recommendation.

Council conclusions are adopted after a debate during a Council meeting. They can contain a political position on a specific topic. Council resolutions usually set out future work foreseen in a specific policy area. They have no legal effect, but they can invite the European Commission to make a proposal or take further action. Before they are adopted, conclusions and resolutions on youth must pass through three levels at the Council:

- The EU working party on youth,
- Permanent Representatives Committee (Coreper), and
- Council configuration.²

The first drafts of resolutions and conclusions are created within the EU working party on youth which is chaired by the Presidency of the EU. The initial texts for these drafts are created by the Presidency. Therefore, the country holding the Presidency is simultaneously responsible for hosting an EUYC, and for drafting conclusions and resolutions on youth. However, conclusions and resolutions are adopted by consensus and require the agreement of all member states. Detailed negotiation may take place, particularly within the EU working party on youth.

This research is a desktop review of the extent to which EUYC recommendations have had an impact on the Resolutions and Conclusion on youth adopted by the Council of the EU through the EU Youth Working Party (hereafter 'Council texts'). It covers the 10 cycles of the dialogue which have taken place to date, during which 30 EUYCs occurred producing 26 sets of conference recommendations between them. The review is based upon identifying the influence of these EUYC recommendations on the 56 Council texts which have been, or are due to be, adopted during the same period.³ (See annex for a full list).

This research was commissioned as part of the Hungarian Presidency (2024) of the Council of the EU.

²<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/council-eu/conclusions-resolutions/#:~:text=The%20Council%20of%20the%20EU%20negotiates%20and%20adopts%20not%20only,the%20EU's%20areas%20of%20Qactivity>.

³The Hungarian 2024 EUYC has yet to take place at the time of writing, however, the format and structure of the recommendations intended to be produced is known. Similarly, two Council texts intended for adoption during the Hungarian Presidency were in draft form at the time of writing. These documents have been analysed to the extent possible.

2. Research Results

2.2 Acknowledgement within Council texts

Of the 56 conclusions and resolutions adopted during the 10 cycles of the dialogue, just under two thirds (n=36) have directly acknowledged or otherwise demonstrated an influence of EUYCs or other parts of the dialogue upon the Council text.

This acknowledgement can occur through any of the following means:

1. Reproduction of a Presidency's EUYC recommendations (either in full or abridged), within the body or annex of the Council text adopted during the same Presidency, (see Section 2.4)
2. Reproduction of recommendations from previous EUYCs within the body or annex of the Council text (see Section 2.5). This typically occurs either as:
 - Collaboration between Presidencies in the same cycle of the dialogue - leading to a Council text being adopted under a Presidency that reproduces or substantially utilises a set of recommendations from an EUYC hosted by a previous Presidency within the same cycle, or,
 - A reference within a Council text to outcomes of the previous dialogue cycles and their recommendations, especially in relation to the EU Youth Goals.
3. A citation of a conference report,
4. Citation or partial reproduction of the dialogue consultation findings, or implementation reports within the Council text
5. A statement of acknowledgement of the dialogue or EUYC within the Council text.

There has been a marked increase in the level of acknowledgement when EUYD and Structured Dialogue are compared. All conclusions or resolutions (n=25) made during EUYD have made some level of acknowledgement, compared to just over one third (n=11, 35%) of those made during Structured Dialogue. To some extent this increase occurs through the repeated use of the EU Youth Goals (created at the end of the Structured Dialogue) as a reference point for Council texts. However, it is also clear that use of recommendations and outputs from EUYCs and the dialogue as a whole is generally much more widespread within EUYD compared to Structured Dialogue.

2.3 Agenda alignment between EUYC recommendations and Council texts

The core themes of Council conclusions and resolutions are not always fully aligned with the theme of EUYC recommendations. An overarching theme for each cycle of the dialogue is usually agreed, and there are typically Council texts relating to this theme. However, other Council texts are often also adopted on topics outside of this theme. It is seemingly a common approach of many Presidencies to direct the recommendations of their EUYCs and toward specific Council texts, whilst addressing other agendas within separate Council texts.

For instance, the German Presidency EUYC was focused on youth participation. Two Council texts were adopted during this Presidency. The first focused on fostering democratic awareness and democratic engagement among young people in Europe ([2020/C 415/09](#)) and incorporated the recommendations of the Presidency EUYC within the body text. The second Council text focused on establishing a European Youth Work Agenda ([2020/C 415/01](#)). Some reference to past EUYC outputs (in the form of EU Youth goals) are made within this second text, but the use of recommendations from the Presidency EUYCs was not extensive beyond this.

In the same manner, a number of Council texts (n=12) relate to what might be termed the functioning of the EU youth sector (such as resolutions on the European Union Work Plans for Youth). These Council texts do not generally align strongly with the recommendations coming from EUYCs, in that EUYCs are usually topic specific.

Overall, 48.2% (n=27) of Council texts are thematically aligned with the major themes of relevant⁴ EUYC recommendations produced in the same cycle, and a further 10.7% (n=6) are partially aligned. This rises to 60.0% (n=15) and 12.0% (n=3) when only the EUYD is considered (see Figure 2a).

This is an important finding, when considering the extent to which EUYC recommendations are directly incorporated into Council texts (see Sections 2.4 & 2.5). It is evidently the case that many Council texts cover different topics to the EUYD, and thus potential for inclusion of EUYC recommendations in these texts is much more limited or was not generally foreseen.

Figure 2a: Agenda Alignment between Council texts and relevant EUYC recommendations

⁴For this purpose, ‘relevant recommendations’ means the EUYC recommendations made during the Presidency in which the Council text was adopted, and/or, previous EUYC recommendations where it was clear the intention of the Council text was to utilise a specific set of prior recommendations from the same Trio of Presidencies in a substantial manner.

2.4 Use of Presidency EUYC recommendations within Council texts

Council conclusions and resolutions were assessed for the extent that they had incorporated recommendations from the EUYC *taking place during the Presidency within which the Council texts were adopted* (hereafter, 'the Presidency EUYC'). Results are shown in Figure 2b

Figure 2b: Council texts including recommendations from Presidency EUYCs

● EUYC recs fully included ● EUYC recs partially included
● EUYC recs not included ● N/A - no EUYC recs produced

Overall, 9 (n=16.1%) of conclusions and resolutions adopted have directly incorporated recommendations in full from the Presidency EUYC. Of the nine documents that fully included EUYC recommendations:

- Three included Presidency EUYC recommendations in the body text,
- Four included Presidency EUYC recommendations within the annex,
- Two included Presidency EUYC recommendations in both the annex and the body text, typically with headline recommendations within the body and supportive text within the annex (e.g. [C/2024/3808](#))

A further 12.5% (n=7) of Council texts have partially included Presidency EUYC recommendations - typically by including an abridged version or summary (e.g. [2011/C 372/03](#)). A further 12.5% (n=7) of Council texts were made during Presidencies where there were no recommendations produced by the presidency EUYC⁵.

⁵The N/A figure excludes the Hungarian 2024 presidency, where the EUYC is yet to take place at the time of writing, but draft Council texts indicate how EUYC recommendations may be used. The N/A figure includes Council texts during four presidencies (Netherlands, Malta, Estonia, Malta, & Austria). These Presidencies either adopted Council texts based on recommendations from EUYCs in the same cycle or worked with later Presidencies in their cycle to incorporate their EUYC outputs into subsequent Council texts. Two of the seven Council texts adopted during these four presidencies

58.9% (n=33) of Council texts did not include presidency EUYC recommendations in any manner. This is partly explained by the lack of alignment between agendas of some Council texts and EUYCs (see Section 2.3). However, a lower use of EUYC recommendations during the Structured Dialogue, compared to the EUYD, seems to play a more significant role.

There is a substantial increase in the extent to which Council texts have taken into account the Presidency EUYC recommendations during EUYD when compared to Structured Dialogue. Within the Structured Dialogue no Council texts included presidency EUYC recommendations in full⁶ and four Council texts (12.9%) included an abridged or summarised version of their presidency EUYC recommendations (Figure 2c). By comparison, all of the nine Council texts which fully included Presidency EUYC recommendations were adopted during the EUYD period. A further three texts in this period have partially included Presidency EUYC recommendations. This accounts for 36% and 12% respectively of the texts adopted during the EUYD period (see Figure 2d).

Figure 2c: Council texts including recommendations from Presidency EUYCs (Structured Dialogue only)

therefore still included EUYC recommendations from past Presidencies in full. For more on use of past EUYCs see Section 2.5.

⁶This figure does not include the two texts which incorporated recommendations from other Presidencies EUYCs in their respective trios (see footnote five).

Figure 2d: Council texts including recommendations from Presidency EUYCs (EUYD only)

2.5 Use of *any* EUYC recommendations within Council texts

Considering the possibility of Council texts to draw on EUYC recommendations from EUYCs occurring during previous Presidencies, the extent to which Council texts had drawn on recommendations from *any* EUYC was also assessed. Results are shown in Figure 2e.

19.6% (n=11) of Council texts included a set of EUYC recommendations in full. A further 30.4% (n=17) included a reference to EUYC recommendations or an abridged version of them (including citation of EU Youth Goals). Half of all Council texts (n=28) did not include EUYC recommendations.

Of the 11 documents that included EUYC recommendations in full,

- Three included EUYC recommendations in the body text,
- Six included EUYC recommendations within the annex,
- Two included EUYC recommendations in both the annex and the body text, typically with headline recommendations within the body and supportive text within the annex.

Figure 2e: Council texts including recommendations from *any* EUYC

There is a substantial increase in the extent to which Council texts have taken into account EUYC recommendations during EUYD when compared to Structured Dialogue. During the Structured Dialogue period 6.5% (n=2) of Council texts included a set of EUYC recommendations in full, and a further 9.7% (n=3) included referenced or abridged versions of recommendations. This compares to EUYD, where 36.0% (n=9) of texts included a set of EUYC recommendations in full and 56.0% (n=14) including a referenced or abridged version (See Figures 2f & 2g).

The way in which EUYC recommendations are referenced or abridged is also a notable difference between Structured Dialogue and EUYD. During the Structured Dialogue period it was common for EUYC conference reports to generate more recommendations, leading to Council texts providing summaries, or shortened highlights of those recommendations. For example, across the three EUYCs within the third cycle of the Structured Dialogue a total of 21 recommendations, each containing three bullet points were created⁷. These were summarised as four bullet points within a resolution on the overview of the Structured Dialogue ([2014/C 183/01](#)).

By comparison during the EUYD period, EUYCs have more often produced shorter, more concise recommendations, enabling them to be reproduced in Council texts in full. Therefore, referencing or abridging was generally used to recall the results of previous cycles, and particularly the EU Youth Goals. For example, the conclusions on the social dimension of a sustainable Europe for youth ([2023/C 185/06](#)), adopted during the 9th cycle of the dialogue, begin by highlighting relevant elements of the EU Youth Goals from the 6th cycle.

⁷Seven recommendations per conference were created. As there is no standard format for recommendations, this could also be interpreted as 63 recommendations, or 7 cumulative recommendations.

Figure 2f: Council texts including recommendations from *any* EUYC (Structured Dialogue only)

Figure 2g: Council texts including recommendations from *any* EUYC (EUJD only)

2.6 Thematic influence of the dialogue on Council texts

As Council texts utilise EUYC recommendations in quite variable ways, the thematic connection between the EUYC recommendations and Council texts was also analysed. Each Council text was compared to relevant EUYC recommendations⁸. Council texts were

⁸See footnote four for a definition of 'relevant' recommendations.

graded against a Likert scale (see Figure 2h) based on the extent to which ideas or concepts within the relevant EUYC recommendations were reflected in the Council text. Particular attention was paid to the elements of the Council text which invite or somehow encourage action from other stakeholders such as EU member states, or the European Commission.

This measure is intended to assess the amount of influence that the EUYC recommendations had on the content of Council texts. However, it should be treated with caution. The presence of similar themes and ideas within both texts, does not necessarily demonstrate that an EUYC recommendation has *caused* a theme or idea to be present within a Council text. Thematic analysis is also subject to a high degree of subjective interpretation.

Results are shown in Figure 2i. They indicate that around 42.8% (n=24) of Council texts showed a *moderate* or *strong connection* to relevant EUYC recommendations. A further 8.9% (n=5) showed a *very strong* connection. However, all of the Council texts receiving this *very strong* rating were resolutions on the outcomes of the Structured Dialogue / EU Youth Dialogue, where the principal purpose of the text was to acknowledge the outcomes of the dialogue.

As with other findings, there is a notable improvement when EUYD and Structured Dialogue are compared (see Figure 2j). 28.0% (n=7) of EUYD Council texts can be assessed as *strong* compared to only 16.0% (n=5) of Structured Dialogue texts. There has also been a substantial reduction in the number of texts which have only a *low / general* connection during EUYD.

Figure 2h: Rating scale

Rating	Description
None	Concepts and ideas within the relevant EUYD recommendations cannot be seen within the Council text
Low / General	Both texts focus on the similar general theme, but there are no extensive connections beyond this, or they focus on different themes with some minor connections
Moderate	There are multiple specific concepts and ideas within the relevant EUYD recommendations that are reflected within the Council text
Strong	There are a large number of specific ideas and concepts within the relevant EUYD recommendations that are reflected within the Council text
Very strong	The major substance of the Council text reflects specific concepts and ideas within the relevant EUYD recommendations, and there are limited concepts or ideas within the Council text that are not within EUYD recommendations
N/A	No presidency EUYC recommendations produced, and no other EUYC recommendations specifically utilised in the Council text

Figure 2i: Thematic connection between relevant EUYC recommendations and Council texts

Figure 2j: Thematic connection between relevant EUYC recommendations and Council texts - Structured Dialogue vs EUYD.

3. Conclusions and summary of results

Assessing the impact of youth participation activities on policy is a challenging endeavour. There are few, if any, widely developed or accepted methodologies for doing so⁹. The Structured Dialogue and the EUYD provide a unique opportunity to undertake this challenge. For more than a decade the dialogue has documented political goals and wishes of young people (in the form of EUYC recommendations) with the intention that these are used to influence a clearly identifiable set of policies, i.e., conclusions and resolutions of the Council of the European Union, made via the EU Working Party on Youth. It is therefore possible to assess the similarities and links between the two sets of texts and chart the changes in this over time.

The extent of thematic similarities, quotations or references to the dialogue process within Council texts clearly demonstrates a significant political attempt by policy makers to take into account the views of young people expressed through the dialogue. Nevertheless, it is important to recognise that Council texts which use phrases such as '*note the following [EUYC recommendations]*' do not automatically signify substantial political action occurs on the specific points. That being said, conclusions and resolutions on youth are not legally binding and instead signal the political position of the Council, 'inviting' other stakeholders to take action. The exact manner in which EUYC recommendations have been cited may therefore not be of huge significance. Those other actors, such as the EU Member States still have a high degree of freedom on which, if any, parts of Council texts they act upon.

With this in mind, it can be said that:

Of the 56 Council resolutions or conclusions on youth passed during the existence of the dialogue process:

- 42.8% (n=24) of Council texts showed a *moderate* or *strong* connection to relevant EUYC recommendations.
- A further 8.9% (n=5) showed a *very strong* connection. These were all resolutions on the outcomes of the Structured Dialogue / EUYD, where the principal purpose was to acknowledge these outcomes.
- 19.6% (n=11) included a set of EUYC recommendations in full, 9 of which were from Presidency EUYCs, with the remaining two coming from other EUYCs in the same cycle.
- A further 30.4% (n=17) included a reference to a set of EUYC recommendations or an abridged version of them (including citation of EU Youth Goals).

There has been a substantial increase in the extent to which Council resolutions or conclusions on youth take into account EUYC recommendations when EUYD and Structured Dialogue are compared. Within the EUYD:

- 60.0% (n=15) of Council texts showed a *moderate* or *strong* connection to relevant EUYC recommendations

⁹Crowley, Anne. "Is anyone listening? The impact of children's participation on public policy." *The International Journal of Children's Rights* 23.3 (2015): 602-621.

- A further 16.0% (n=4) showed a *very strong* connection. These were all resolutions on the outcomes of the Structured Dialogue / EUYD, where the principal purpose was to acknowledge these outcomes.
- 36.0% (n=9) of texts included a set of EUYC recommendations in full and 56.0% (n=14) including a referenced or abridged version (including citation of EU Youth Goals).

This increase is likely explained by:

- The EUYD period is seemingly marked by greater political commitment by the EU Youth Working party to directly include EUYC recommendations.
- Linked to the above, EUYCs within the EUYD period have generally created shorter, more concise recommendations, making them more practical to include within Council texts in full.
- The production of the EU Youth Goals at the end of the Structured Dialogue has provided a framework of EUYC recommendations that have been repeatedly referenced during subsequent cycles of the EUYD, leading to an increase in the number of times EUYC recommendations are referenced or cited.

When considering the Council resolutions and conclusions where EUYC recommendation have had less identifiable influence, the most substantial factor seems to be the difference between Structured Dialogue and EUYD described above. However, lack of alignment between EUYC themes and Council text themes also plays a role. Overall, around 35.7% (n=20) of Council texts were not theoretically aligned with the major themes of EUYC relevant recommendation. This falls to 28.0% (n=7) when only the EUYD is considered. It is seemingly a common approach of many presidencies to direct the recommendations of their EUYCs and youth dialogue efforts toward specific Council texts, whilst still addressing other agendas within separate Council texts.

On the one hand, this might be regarded as a necessary approach to policy making, retaining the Council's autonomy to pursue agendas without the involvement of the dialogue. However, it can also be said that there are missed opportunities to utilise the EUYCs to inform many Council texts and that the EUYC recommendations are not systematically considered when *all* Council resolutions and conclusions are passed.

The extent to which the dialogue process can be considered effective at impacting upon policy is a challenging question. Theories and discourse about youth participation typically assume that maximising influence of young people to the greatest extent possible is the goal¹⁰. However, theories and discourse about policy making, generally recognise that citizens' participation is one driver of policy, but that other drivers, such as research, decision of elected officials and insight from professionals all can and should influence policy¹¹. It is probably not a reasonable expectation that all aspects of Council texts should be based fully on the views and opinions of young people.

¹⁰ Hart, Roger. *Children's Participation: From Tokenism to Citizenship*, UNICEF, 1992.

¹¹ Denstad, Finn Yrjar. *Youth Policy Manual: How to develop a national youth strategy*. Council of Europe, 2009.

With this in mind, it can be concluded that, at least since the start of EUYD, a large proportion of Council resolutions and conclusions adopted via the EU Working Party on Youth have taken into account the views of young people expressed through the dialogue process to a considerable extent. In general, there is a clear and demonstrable link between the young people's voices and published policy documents, and it can be understood that policy makers have a genuine commitment to incorporate the EUYD outcomes into these Council texts.

Three gaps can be identified, all of which related to the way policy agendas are determined:

- 1) **Agenda setting** - for the most part, EUYCs produce recommendations on the agendas set by the Presidency, or TRIO of Presidencies within a cycle. This occurs firstly through the choice of theme of the EUYD cycle, and secondly through the thematic topics of working groups within an EUYC. The former sets the general theme of EUYC recommendations, and the latter tends to guide the sub topics within them. Whilst many Presidencies do work collaboratively with their national youth councils to choose these themes and topics, the ability of the EUYD to produce recommendations on topics outside of Presidency defined agendas is generally limited. i.e., whilst the dialogue enables young people to influence development of existing policy agendas, it is less effective at enabling young people to set policy agendas or determine the topics of policy agendas outside of Presidency priorities.
- 2) **Agenda alignment** - Whilst the EU Working Party on Youth has shown ever increasing commitments to incorporate EUYC recommendations and dialogue outputs into Council texts, it is clear that not all Council texts systematically take into account the outputs of the EUYD. In other words, distinct policy agendas are often developed or pursued by the EU Working Party on Youth in parallel to the set agendas of the EUYD. These distinct agendas result in Council and recommendations where EUYD has not been utilised as extensively to provide input.
- 3) **Influencing agendas outside of the youth field** - This research only takes into account Council texts adopted through the EU Working Party on Youth. However, it is clear that many EUYC recommendations relate, at least in part, to policy agendas outside of the youth field (e.g. formal education, housing, transport). Though examples of Council texts adopted via other working parties which take into account EUYD outputs do exist (e.g., [C/2023/1339](#)) these are generally limited. As a result, the scope of EUYD to influence agendas outside of the youth field can also be understood to be more limited.

4. Recommendations

To further maximise the already strong impact of EUYD on policy, the stakeholders connected to EUYD could take the following actions.

The EU Working Party on Youth could:

- 1) Continue to centralise the EUYC recommendations within Council resolutions and conclusions, and work to ensure that content and ideas within EUYC recommendations have the meaningful potential to affect the substantive content and ideas elsewhere in Council texts adopted through the EU Working Party on Youth.

- 2) Continue the practice of passing a dedicated resolution on the outcomes of each cycle of the EUYD, which should contain all EUYC recommendations from the cycle. This practice should be used primarily for taking note, cataloguing, and archiving of EUYC recommendations. It should be understood that substantive work of incorporating these recommendations into policy needs to happen through other resolutions and conclusions.
- 3) Systematically review all historic EUYC recommendations when developing new Council conclusions or recommendations. Many past EUYC recommendations still contain relevant content and ideas which can inform policy development.
- 4) Consider how *all* Council resolutions and conclusions tabled for discussion through the EU Working Party on Youth can be discussed within the EUYC. In other words, it should be considered if all agendas being pursued by the EU Working Party on Youth can be brought, in some way, to the EUYC conference floor for discussion, or can take into account EUYD outputs through other means.

EUYC conference organisers could:

- 5) In connection with point four above, ensure the agendas and working groups within the EUYC cover all policy agendas being pursued by the EU Working Party on Youth at any one time.
- 6) Adopt a semi-standard format, length, and naming terminology for EUYC outputs. Between 5-10 recommendations per major theme, each around one sentence long and covering a distinct sub-topic seems to be optimal for direct inclusion in the body of Council texts. This can be supported by further explanatory text within the annexes of Council texts or conference reports. The possibility to depart from this standard might be necessary in some instances, depending on the policy agendas pursued.
- 7) Consider utilising open space methodologies to give EUYC participants greater influence over the subtopics within a set of EUYC recommendations, whilst also taking into account input from EUYD consultation within this process.

The EU Youth Coordinator and the European Commission could:

- 8) Continue to develop processes for youth mainstreaming. Fostering concrete methods for bringing the EUYC recommendations and other EUYD outputs into European policy discussions outside of the youth field, as well to the EU Working Parties on topics other than youth. The area of formal education, which is frequently raised through EUYD, and is closely connected to the youth field could be considered a priority policy area.
- 9) Consider developing processes for monitoring and reporting on the impact of EUYD, such as those currently being proposed through the EESC Own Opinion Initiative on Strengthening the EU Youth Dialogue follow-up via monitoring and transparency guidelines¹².

¹²[Strengthening the EU Youth Dialogue follow-up via monitoring and transparency guidelines | EESC, forthcoming](#)

The EUYD European Steering Group, in consultation with all other actors involved in EUYD could:

- 10) Agree a time at which it will be necessary to update or refresh the EU Youth Goals through the EUYD. The EU Youth Goals have formed a highly useful framework for incorporating EUYD outputs into Council texts. As the concerns of young people change over time, it will be necessary to refresh them. Considering that the EU Youth Strategy, to which the goals are currently annexed, lasts until 2027, it may be optimal to connect any updated version of the EU Youth Goals to any subsequent EU Youth Strategies.
- 11) Consider how the EUYD can be used more effectively to influence agenda setting within the EU Working Party on Youth. For example, elements of the EUYD consultation / dialogue phases or conferences could be conducted without pre-set themes and with the primary purpose of prioritising issues for young people upon which future policy developments are needed.

National Working Groups within the EUYD could:

- 12) Undertake desktop reviews of national EUYD outputs to determine the extent to which the dialogue process has impacted upon national policy. This may require European level coordination and additional resourcing.

Annex 1: Council Texts

Council text	Link	Presidency	Year	Cycle
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the active inclusion of young people: combating unemployment and poverty (2010/C 137/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A42010X0527%2801%29	Spain	2010	1
Council conclusions of 19 November 2010 on the European and International Policy Agendas on Children, Youth and Children's Rights (2010/C 326/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52010XG1203%2801%29	Belgium	2010	1
Council conclusions of 19 November 2010 on access of young people to culture (2010/C 326/02)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:326:0002:0003:EN:PDF	Belgium	2010	1
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on youth work (2010/C 327/01)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:327:0001:0005:EN:PDF	Belgium	2010	1
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the structured dialogue with young people on youth employment (2011/C 164/01)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:164:0001:0004:EN:PDF	Hungary	2011	1
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on encouraging new and effective forms of participation of all young people in democratic life in Europe (2011/C 169/01)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:169:0001:0005:EN:PDF	Hungary	2011	1
Council conclusions on the eastern dimension of youth participation and mobility (2011/C 372/03)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:372:0010:0014:EN:PDF	Poland	2011	2
Council conclusions of 11 May 2012 on fostering the creative and innovative potential of young people (2012/C 169/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52012XG0615%2801%29	Denmark	2012	2
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, of 27 November 2012 on the participation and social inclusion of young people with emphasis on those with a migrant background (2012/C 393/05)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2012:393:0015:0019:EN:PDF	Cyprus	2012	2
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the overview of the structured dialogue with young people on youth participation in democratic life in Europe (2012/C 380/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2012:380:0001:0004:EN:PDF	Cyprus	2012	2
Council conclusions on the contribution of quality youth work to the development, well-being and social inclusion of young people (2013/C 168/03)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2013:168:0005:0009:EN:PDF	Ireland	2013	3
Council conclusions on maximising the potential of youth policy in addressing the goals of the Europe 2020 Strategy (2013/C 224/02)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2013:224:0002:0006:EN:PDF	Ireland	2013	3
Council conclusions on enhancing the social inclusion of young people not in employment, education or training (2014/C 30/03)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52014XG0201(02)	Lithuania	2014	3
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, of 20 May 2014 on the overview of the structured dialogue process including social inclusion of young people (2014/C 183/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42014Y0614(01)&from=CS	Greece	2014	3

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, of 20 May 2014 on a European Union Work Plan for Youth for 2014-2015 (2014/C 183/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42014Y0614(02)&from=CS	Greece	2014	3
Council conclusions of 20 May 2014 on promoting youth entrepreneurship to foster social inclusion of young people (2014/C 183/04)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52014XG0614(04)&from=CS	Greece	2014	3
Council conclusions on promoting young people's access to rights in order to foster their autonomy and participation in civil society (2015/C 18/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015XG0121(01)&from=CS	Italy	2014	4
Council conclusions on reinforcing youth work to ensure cohesive societies (2015/C 170/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015XG0523(01)&from=CS	Latvia	2015	4
Council conclusions on enhancing cross-sectorial policy cooperation to effectively address socio economic challenges facing young people (2015/C 172/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015XG0527(01)&from=CS	Latvia	2015	4
Council Resolution on encouraging political participation of young people in democratic life in Europe (2015/C 417/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42015Y1215(02)&from=CS	Luxembourg	2015	4
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on a European Union Work Plan for Youth for 2016-2018 (2015/C 417/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42015Y1215(01)&from=CS	Luxembourg	2015	4
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the prevention of radicalisation leading to violent extremism (2016/C 467/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016XG1215(01)&from=CS	Netherlands	2016	5
Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on promoting new approaches in youth work to uncover and develop the potential of young people (2016/C 467/03)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016XG1215(02)&from=CS	Slovakia	2016	5
Council conclusions on strategic perspectives for European cooperation in the youth field post-2018 (2017/C 189/07)	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52017XG0615(02)&from=EN	Malta	2017	5
Council Conclusions on the role of youth work in supporting young people's development of essential life skills that facilitate their successful transition to adulthood, active citizenship and working life (2017/C 189/06)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52017XG0615(01)&from=EN	Malta	2017	5
Council Resolution on the Structured Dialogue and the future development of the dialogue with young people in the context of policies for European cooperation in the youth field, post 2018 (2017/C 189/01)	EUR-Lex - 32017G0615(01) - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)	Malta	2017	5
Council conclusions on smart youth work (2017/C 418/02)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52017XG1207(01)&from=CS	Estonia	2017	6
Council conclusions on the role of youth in addressing the demographic challenges within the European Union (2018/C 196/04)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018XG0608(01)&from=CS	Bulgaria	2018	6
Council conclusions on the role of young people in building a secure, cohesive and harmonious society in Europe (2018/C 195/05)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018XG0607(02)&from=CS	Bulgaria	2018	6
Council conclusions on the role of youth work in the context of migration and refugee matters (2018/C 441/03)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018XG1207(02)&from=CS	Austria	2018	6

Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a framework for European cooperation in the youth field: The European Union Youth Strategy 2019-2027(2018/C 456/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:2018:456:FULL&from=EN	Austria	2018	6
Council Conclusions on Young People and the Future of Work (2019/C 189/05)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019XG0605(02)&from=CS	Romania	2019	7
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Member States meeting within the Council establishing guidelines on the governance of the EU Youth Dialogue — European Union Youth Strategy 2019-2027 (2019/C 189/01)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42019Y0605(01)&from=EN	Romania	2019	7
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on education and training of youth workers 2019/C 412/03	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019XG1209(01)&qid=1576066581699	Finland	2019	7
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on Digital Youth Work 2019/C 414/02	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019XG1210(01)&from=CS	Finland	2019	7
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the Outcomes of the 7th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue European Union Youth Strategy 2020/C 2121/01	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42020Y0626(01)&qid=1594102713230&from=CS	Croatia	2020	7
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on raising opportunities for young people in rural and remote areas 2020/C 193/06	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020XG0609(01)&from=CS	Croatia	2020	7
Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on fostering democratic awareness and democratic engagement among young people in Europe 2020/C 415/0	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020XG1201(01)&from=CS	Germany	2020	8
Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the Framework for establishing a European Youth Work Agenda 2020/C 415/01	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42020Y1201(01)&from=CS	Germany	2020	8
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on strengthening the multilevel governance when promoting the participation of young people in decision-making processes 2021/C 241/03	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021XG0621(01)&from=CS	Portugal	2021	8
Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on safeguarding and creating civic spaces for young people that facilitate meaningful youth participation (2021/C 501 I/04	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021XG1213(04)&from=CS	Slovenia	2021	8
Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the EU Youth Strategy Work Plan 2022-2024 (2021/C 504 I/01	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42021Y1214(02)&from=CS	Slovenia	2021	8
Council conclusions on the implementation of the EU Youth Strategy (2019-2021) 2021/C 504 I/02	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021XG1214(10)&from=CS	Slovenia	2021	8
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the outcomes of the 8th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue 2021/C 504/0	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42021Y1214(01)&from=CS	Slovenia	2021	8
Conclusions of the Council and the representatives of the governments of the Member States, meeting within the	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:5	France	2022	9

Council – Fostering engagement among young people as actors of change in order to protect the environment (2022/C 159/07)	2022XG0412(01)&from=CS			
Conclusions of the Council and the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on promoting the intergenerational dimension in the youth field to foster dialogue and social cohesion	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022XG1229(01)	Czechia	2022	9
Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the revision of the EU Youth Strategy Work Plan 2022-2024	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A42023Y0526%2802%29&qid=1685097238501	Sweden	2023	9
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the outcomes of the 9th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (2023/C 185/04)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A42023Y0526%2801%29&qid=1685097189890	Sweden	2023	9
Conclusions of the Council and the representatives of the governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council on the social dimension of a sustainable Europe for youth (2023/C 185/06)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52023XG0526%2801%29&qid=1685097096881	Sweden	2023	9
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on promoting youth mainstreaming in policy decision-making processes in the European Union (C/2023/1342)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:C_202301342	Spain	2023	10
Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States on a comprehensive approach to the mental health of young people in the European Union	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:C_202301337	Spain	2023	10
Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on inclusive societies for young people (C/2024/3808)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C_202403808	Belgium	2024	10
Conclusions of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the European and international policy agendas on children, youth and children's rights (C/2024/3528)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C_202403528	Belgium	2024	10
Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on youth work policy in an empowering Europe (C/2024/3526)	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C_202403526	Belgium	2024	10
Draft conclusions on providing global opportunities for young people living in rural and remote areas	DRAFT TEXT	Hungary	2024	10
Draft resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the outcomes of the 10th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue	DRAFT TEXT	Hungary	2024	10

Annex 2: List of EU Youth Conferences

Presidency	Year	Cycle	Source text used to identify conference recommendations
Spain	2010	1	Compendium Of The First Cycle Of The Structured Dialogue
Belgium	2010	1	Conference report or equivalent
Hungary	2011	1	Conference report or equivalent
Poland	2011	2	Conference report or equivalent
Denmark	2012	2	Conference report or equivalent
Cyprus	2012	2	Conference report or equivalent
Ireland	2013	3	Conference report or equivalent
Lithuania	2013	3	Conference report or equivalent
Greece	2014	3	Conference report or equivalent
Italy	2014	4	Conference report or equivalent
Latvia	2015	4	Conference report or equivalent
Luxembourg	2015	4	Conference report or equivalent
Netherlands	2016	5	No recommendations identified; Presidency worked collaboratively to generate one set of recommendations under Slovakian EUYC
Slovakia	2016	5	Conference report or equivalent
Malta	2017	5	No EUYC recommendations; Presidency worked collaboratively to generate one set of recommendations under Slovakian EUYC
Estonia	2017	6	No recommendations produced, Presidency worked collaboratively to produce EU Youth Goals
Bulgaria	2018	6	EU Youth Goals
Austria	2018	6	No recommendations produced; Presidency worked collaboratively to produce EU Youth Goals
Romania	2019	7	Conference report or equivalent
Finland	2019	7	Conference report or equivalent
Croatia	2020	7	Conference report or equivalent
Germany	2020	8	Conference report or equivalent
Portugal	2021	8	Draft conference report
Slovenia	2021	8	Conference report or equivalent
France	2022	9	Conference report or equivalent
Czechia	2022	9	Conference report or equivalent
Sweden	2023	9	Conference report or equivalent
Spain	2023	10	Conference report or equivalent
Belgium	2024	10	Conference report or equivalent
Hungary	2024	10	Conference yet to take place at time of writing, workshop planning notes used to identify the structure of recommendations.